

Contra Continuous and Irresolute Maps via M -open Sets in n -Cylindrical Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

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Abstract. In this paper, n -cylindrical neutrosophic contra M -continuous mappings are defined and investigated within the framework of n -cylindrical neutrosophic topological spaces. Motivated by recent developments on neutrosophic contra continuous functions, irresolute mappings, and n -cylindrical fuzzy neutrosophic topological structures, several fundamental properties of n -cylindrical neutrosophic contra M -irresolute mappings are established. The results obtained extend and complement existing studies on various classes of neutrosophic contra continuous and contra irresolute mappings, thereby enriching the theory of neutrosophic topological spaces and providing a basis for further applications of n -cylindrical neutrosophic mappings.

Keywords: n -CyN \mathcal{C} Mos, n -CyN \mathcal{C} MCts map, and n -CyN \mathcal{C} MIrr map.

1. Introduction

Following Zadeh's introduction of fuzzy set (denoted as fs) in 1965 [24], Chang [6] developed the notion of fuzzy topological spaces (fts), which led to the adaptation of classical topological concepts within the framework of fuzzy topology by various researchers. A significant generalization of fuzzy sets, known as intuitionistic fuzzy set (ifs), was introduced by Atanassov in 1986 [4]. Building on this, Coker [7] introduced the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces ($ifts$) based on ifs . Jeon et al. [9] further investigated intuitionistic fuzzy continuity and pre-continuity within this framework.

With the advent of neutrosophy and neutrosophic sets by Smarandache [16], a new direction in uncertainty modeling emerged. Salama and Alblowi [12] introduced neutrosophic crisp

sets and neutrosophic topological spaces (Nts), extending $ifts$ and incorporating degrees of membership, indeterminacy, and non-membership for each element. Neutrosophic has formed the foundation for a broader class of theories that generalize both crisp and fuzzy structures.

Smarandache also introduced the concept of dependence degrees between fuzzy and neutrosophic components. Later, Arokiarani et al. [3] introduced the neutrosophic set (NS), wherein the sum of the three membership values does not exceed 3. In the same year, Veereswari [23] proposed the notion of neutrosophic topological spaces (Nts) and studied fundamental operations on them.

Saranya et al. [13] introduced the concept of n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets (abbreviated as n - $CyNS$'s), characterized by α and γ as dependent components and β as an independent component. Apart from neutrosophic set (NS), n - $CyNS$ represents the most extensive generalization of fuzzy sets (fs). In this framework, the membership functions positive (α), neutral (β), and negative (γ) satisfy the conditions $0 \leq \beta_A \leq 1$ and $0 \leq \alpha_A^n(x) + \gamma_A^n(x) \leq 1$, $n > 1$, where $n > 1$ is an integer.

Later, Saranya et al. [15] introduced the notion of n - CyN continuity for functions between two n -cylindrical neutrosophic topological spaces (n - $CyNts$). They also defined the n - CyN interior (n - $CyNint$) and n - CyN closure (n - $CyNcl$) of subsets within n - $CyNts$.

In a related development, El-Maghrabi and Al-Juhani [8] introduced the concept of M -open sets in topological spaces and investigated several of their properties. The class of M -open sets plays a significant role in topological theory due to its applicability across various branches of mathematics and real-world applications. Padma et al. [11] also found M -open sets in nano topological spaces. Vadivel et al. [17–19] discussed some open sets in fuzzy nano and neutrosophic nano topological spaces. Kalaiyarsan et al. [10] and Vadivel et al. [20–22] introduced M -open sets and $\delta\beta$ open sets in fuzzy, Pythagorean fuzzy and neutrosophic nano topological spaces. Balasubramanian et al. [5] introduced contra continuous and irresolute maps in Pythagorean fuzzy nano topological spaces. Building on this, Anandhi et al. [1] introduced the concept of n -cylindrical neutrosophic topological spaces n - $CyNts$ based on n - $CyNS$'s. Anandhi et al. [2] further investigated n -cylindrical neutrosophic M -continuous and M -irresolute within this framework.

The subsequent sections of this dissertation are organized as follows: Section 2 provides a brief review of fundamental definitions related to intuitionistic fuzzy sets (ifs 's), neutrosophic sets (NS 's), n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets (n - $CyNS$'s) and mappings on n -cylindrical neutrosophic topological spaces (n - $CyNts$). Sections 3 and 4 introduce the concepts of n - $CyN\mathcal{C}MCts$ and n - $CyN\mathcal{C}MIrr$ within n - $CyNts$, along with an exploration of their fundamental properties supported by illustrative examples. Finally, the dissertation concludes with a summary of findings in Section 5.

2. Preliminaries

This section covers some basic definitions and examples that will be useful in subsequent discussions.

Definition 2.1. [24] A fuzzy set (briefly, *fs*) A in X is defined by membership function $\mu_A : A \rightarrow [0, 1]$ whose membership value $\mu_A(x)$ shows the degree to which $x \in X$ includes in the fuzzy set A , for all $x \in X$.

Definition 2.2. [6] A fuzzy topological space (briefly, *fts*) is a pair (X, τ) , where X is any set and τ is a family of fuzzy sets in X satisfying following axioms:

- (i) $\phi, X \in \tau$,
- (ii) If $A, B \in \tau$, then $A \cap B \in \tau$,
- (iii) If $A_i \in \tau$ for each $i \in I$, then $\cup A_i \in \tau$.

Definition 2.3. [4] An intuitionistic fuzzy set (briefly, *ifs*) A on X is an object of the form $A = \{\langle x, \alpha_A(x), \gamma_A(x) : x \in X \rangle\}$ where $\alpha_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ is called the degree of positive membership of x in A , $\gamma_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ is called the degree of negative membership of x in A , and where $\alpha_A(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x)$ satisfy (for all $x \in X$) $(\alpha_A(x) + \gamma_A(x) \leq 1)$ $ifs(X)$ denotes the set of all the *ifs*'s on X .

Definition 2.4. [16] An neutrosophic set A on X is an object of the form $A = \{\langle x, \alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x), \gamma_A(x) : x \in X \rangle\}$, where $\alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \in [0, 1], 0 \leq \alpha_A(x) + \beta_A(x) + \gamma_A(x) \leq 3$, for all $x \in X$. $\alpha_A(x)$ is the degree of positive membership, $\beta_A(x)$ is the degree of neutral and $\gamma_A(x)$ is the degree of negative membership. Here, $\alpha_A(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x)$ are dependent components and $\beta_A(x)$ is an independent component.

Definition 2.5. [12] An neutrosophic topology (*Nt*) on a non-empty set X is a family τ_N of neutrosophic subsets in X satisfying the following axioms:

- (i) $0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N$,
- (ii) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau_N$ for any $G_1, G_2 \in \tau_N$,
- (iii) $\cup G_i \in \tau_N$, for all $\{G_i : i \in J\} \subseteq \tau_N$.

In this case the pair (X, τ_N) is called a neutrosophic topological spaces (briefly, *Nts*) and any neutrosophic set in τ is known as neutrosophic open set (briefly, *Nos*) in X . The elements of τ_X are called neutrosophic open sets. A neutrosophic set F is closed if and only if $C(F)$ is neutrosophic open.

Definition 2.6. [13] An n -cylindrical neutrosophic set (briefly, *n-CyNS*) A on X is an object of the form $A = \{\langle x, \alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x), \gamma_A(x) : x \in X \rangle\}$, where $\alpha_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ called the degree of positive membership of x in A , $\beta_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ called the degree of neutral membership of x in A , $\gamma_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ called the degree of negative membership of x in A , and where $\alpha_A(x) + \beta_A(x) + \gamma_A(x) \leq 3$, for all $x \in X$.

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x in A and $\gamma_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ called the degree of negative membership of x in A , which satisfies the condition: (for all $x \in X$) ($0 \leq \beta_A(x) \leq 1$) and $0 \leq \alpha_A^n(x) + \gamma_A^n(x) \leq 1$, $n > 1$, is an integer. Here, $\alpha_A(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x)$ are dependent neutrosophic components and $\beta_A(x)$ is 100% independent.

For the convenience, $\langle \alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle$ is called as n -cylindrical neutrosophic number (briefly, n -CyNN) and is denoted as $A = \{\langle \alpha_A, \beta_A, \gamma_A \rangle\}$.

Definition 2.7. [13] Let $\{A_i : i \in I\}$ be an arbitrary family of n -CyNS in X . Then, $\cap A_i = \{\langle x, \inf(\alpha_{A_i}(x)), \inf(\beta_{A_i}(x)), \sup(\gamma_{A_i}(x)) \rangle : x \in X\}$. $\cup A_i = \{\langle x, \sup(\alpha_{A_i}(x)), \sup(\beta_{A_i}(x)), \inf(\gamma_{A_i}(x)) \rangle : x \in X\}$.

Definition 2.8. [13] $0_{CyN} = \{\langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X\}$ and $1_{CyN} = \{\langle x, 1, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X\}$

Definition 2.9. [13] (**The Basic Connectives**) Let $\tau_{CyN}(X)$ denote the family of all n -CyNS's on X .

Definition 2.10. [13] Inclusion: For every two $A, B \in \tau_{CyN}(X)$, the inclusion of two n -CyNS's A and B is $A \subseteq B$ iff (for all $x \in X$, $\alpha_A(x) \leq \alpha_B(x)$ and $\beta_A(x) \leq \beta_B(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_B(x)$) and ($A \subseteq B$ and $B \subseteq A$).

Definition 2.11. [13] Union: For every two $A, B \in \tau_{CyN}(X)$, the union of two n -CyNS's A and B is $A \cup B(x) = \{\langle x, \max(\alpha_A(x), \alpha_B(x)), \max(\beta_A(x), \beta_B(x)), \min(\gamma_A(x), \gamma_B(x)) \rangle : x \in X\}$.

Definition 2.12. [13] Intersection: For every two $A, B \in \tau_{CyN}(X)$, the intersection of two n -CyNS's A and B is

$$A \cap B(x) = \{\langle x, \min(\alpha_A(x), \alpha_B(x)), \min(\beta_A(x), \beta_B(x)), \max(\gamma_A(x), \gamma_B(x)) \rangle : x \in X\}.$$

Definition 2.13. [13] Complementary: For every $A \in \tau_{CyN}(X)$, the complement of an n -CyNS A is $A^c = \{\langle x, \gamma_A(x), 1 - \beta_A(x), \alpha_A(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$.

Definition 2.14. [13] Sum: For every two $A, B \in \tau_{CyN}(X)$, the sum of two n -CyNS's A and B is $A \oplus B(x) = \{\langle x, (\frac{\alpha_A(x) \cdot \alpha_B(x)}{\alpha_A(x) + \alpha_B(x)}), \max(\beta_A(x), \beta_B(x)), \min(\gamma_A(x), \gamma_B(x)) \rangle : x \in X\}$.

Definition 2.15. [13] Difference: For every two $A, B \in \tau_{CyN}(X)$, the difference of two n -CyNS's A and B is $A \ominus B(x) = \{\langle x, \max(\alpha_A(x), \alpha_B(x)), \min(\beta_A(x), \beta_B(x)), (\frac{\gamma_A(x) \cdot \gamma_B(x)}{\gamma_A(x) + \gamma_B(x)}) \rangle : x \in X\}$.

Definition 2.16. [13] Product: For every two $A, B \in \tau_{CyN}(X)$, the product of two n -CyNS's A and B is $A \otimes B(x) = \{\langle x, (\alpha_A(x) \cdot \alpha_B(x)), (\beta_A(x) \cdot \beta_B(x)), (\gamma_A(x) \cdot \gamma_B(x)) \rangle : x \in X\}$.

Definition 2.17. [13] Division: For every two $A, B \in \tau_{CyN}(X)$, the division of two n -CyNS's A and B is $A \oslash B(x) = \{\langle x, \min(\alpha_A(x), \alpha_B(x)), (\beta_A(x) \cdot \beta_B(x)), \max(\gamma_A(x), \gamma_B(x)) \rangle : x \in X\}$.

Remark 2.18. [13]

- (i) If $A \subseteq B$ and $B \subseteq C$ then $A \subseteq C$,
- (ii) $A \cup B = B \cup A$ & $A \cap B = B \cap A$,
- (iii) $(A \cup B) \cup C = A \cup (B \cup C)$ & $(A \cap B) \cap C = A \cap (B \cap C)$,
- (iv) $(A \cup B) \cap C = (A \cap C) \cup (B \cap C)$ & $(A \cap B) \cup C = (A \cup C) \cap (B \cup C)$,
- (v) $A \cap A = A$ & $A \cup A = A$,
- (vi) De Morgan's Law for A & B ie., $(A \cup B)^c = A^c \cap B^c$ & $(A \cap B)^c = A^c \cup B^c$,
- (vii) $(A \oplus B) = (B \oplus A)$,
- (viii) $(A \otimes B) = (B \otimes A)$.

Definition 2.19. [15] An n -cylindrical neutrosophic topology (briefly, n - $CyNt$) on a non-empty set X is a family, τ_{CyN} , of n - $CyNS$ in X which satisfies the following conditions:

- (i) $0_{CyN}, 1_{CyN} \in \tau_{CyN}$,
- (ii) $A_1 \cap A_2 \in \tau_{CyN}$,
- (iii) $\cup A_i \in \tau_{CyN}$, for any arbitrary family $A_i \in \tau_{CyN}, i \in I$.

The pair (X, τ_{CyN}) is called an n -cylindrical neutrosophic topological Spaces (briefly, n - $CyNts$) and any n - $CyNS$ belongs to τ_{CyN} is called an n -cylindrical neutrosophic open set (briefly, n - $CyNos$) and the complement of n - $CyNos$ is called n -cylindrical neutrosophic closed set (briefly, n - $CyNcs$) in X . Like classical topological spaces and fuzzy topological spaces, the family $\{0_{CyN}, 1_{CyN}\}$ is called in discrete n - $CyNts$ and the topology containing all the n - CyN subsets is called discrete n - $CyNts$.

Remark 2.20. [15] Obviously any fuzzy topological spaces or intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces or Pythagorean fuzzy topological spaces is an n - $CyNts$ as any subsets of the fuzzy spaces, intuitionistic fuzzy space, and Pythagorean fuzzy space can be viewed as n - CyN subsets.

Definition 2.21. [15] Let A and B be two n -cylindrical neutrosophic subsets of an n - $CyNts$. B is called neighborhood of A if there exists an n - $CyNos$, O such that $A \subset O \subset B$.

Proposition 2.22. [15] $A \subset X$ is n -cylindrical neutrosophic open in (X, τ_{CyN}) if and only if it carries a neighborhood of its subsets.

Definition 2.23. [15] Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n - $CyNts$ and let $A = \{ \langle x, \alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ is an n - $CyNS$ in X . Then, the n -cylindrical neutrosophic interior (briefly, n - $CyNint$) is defined as the n - CyN union of all n - CyN open subsets of X . ie, n - $CyNint(A) = \bigcup \{ G : G \in \tau_{CyN} \text{ and } G \subseteq A \}$.

Clearly, n - $CyNint(A)$ is the biggest n - $CyNos$ that is contained by A .

Definition 2.24. [15] Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n - $CyNts$ and let $A = \{ \langle x, \alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ is an n - $CyNS$ in X . Then, the n -cylindrical neutrosophic closure (briefly, n - $CyNcl$) is defined as the n - CyN intersection of all n - CyN closed subsets of X . ie, n - $CyNcl(A) = \bigcap \{ K : K \in \tau_{CyN} \text{ and } A \subseteq K \}$.

Clearly, n - $CyNcl(A)$ is the smallest n - $CyNcs$ that contains A .

Definition 2.25. [14] Let (X, τ_1) and (Y, τ_2) be two n - $CyNts$ and let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be a n - CyN function. Then, f said to be n - CyN continuous (briefly, n - $CyNcts$) map if for any n -cylindrical neutrosophic subset A of X and for any neighborhood \mathfrak{V} of $f(A)$ there exists a neighborhood \mathfrak{U} of A such that $f(\mathfrak{U}) \subseteq \mathfrak{V}$.

Definition 2.26. [1] Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n - $CyNts$ and A be an n - $CyNS$. Then, A is said to be an n - CyN

- (i) regular open set (briefly, n - $CyNros$), if $A = n$ - $CyNint(n$ - $CyNcl(A))$,
- (ii) regular closed set (briefly, n - $CyNrcs$), if $A = n$ - $CyNcl(n$ - $CyNint(A))$.

Definition 2.27. [1] Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n - $CyNts$ and $A = \{ \langle x, \alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be an n - $CyNS$ in X . Then, the n -cylindrical neutrosophic δ -interior of A and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic δ -closure of A are denoted by n - $CyN\delta int(A)$ and n - $CyN\delta cl(A)$ are defined as follows:

- (i) n - $CyN\delta int(A) = \bigcup \{ G \mid G \text{ is an } n$ - $CyNros \text{ and } G \subseteq A \}$,
- (ii) n - $CyN\delta cl(A) = \bigcap \{ K \mid K \text{ is an } n$ - $CyNrcs \text{ and } A \subseteq K \}$.

Definition 2.28. [1] Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n - $CyNts$ and $A = \{ \langle x, \alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be an n - $CyNS$ in X . Then, the n -cylindrical neutrosophic θ -interior of A and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic θ -closure of A are denoted by n - $CyN\theta int(A)$ and n - $CyN\theta cl(A)$ are defined as follows:

- (i) n - $CyN\theta int(A) = \bigcup \{ n$ - $CyNint(B) : B \subseteq A \text{ \& } B \text{ is a } n$ - $CyNcs \text{ in } X \}$,
- (ii) n - $CyN\theta cl(A) = \bigcap \{ n$ - $CyNcl(B) : A \subseteq B \text{ \& } B \text{ is a } n$ - $CyNos \text{ in } X \}$.

Definition 2.29. [1] Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n - $CyNts$ and $A = \{ \langle x, \alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be an n - $CyNS$ in X . A set A is said to be n - CyN

- (i) δ -open set (briefly, n - $CyN\delta os$), if $A = n$ - $CyN\delta int(A)$,
- (ii) δ -pre open set (briefly, n - $CyN\delta P os$), if $A \subseteq n$ - $CyN\delta int(A)$,
- (iii) δ -semi open set (briefly, n - $CyN\delta S os$), if $A \subseteq n$ - $CyNcl(n$ - $CyN\delta int(A))$,
- (iv) θ -open set (briefly, n - $CyN\theta os$), if $A = n$ - $CyN\theta int(A)$,
- (v) θ -semi open set (briefly, n - $CyN\theta S os$), if $A \subseteq n$ - $CyNcl(n$ - $CyN\theta int(A))$,
- (vi) e -open set (briefly, n - $CyNe os$), if $A = n$ - $CyNcl(n$ - $CyN\delta int(A)) \cup n$ - $CyNint(n$ - $CyN\delta cl(A))$,

(vii) M -open set (briefly, n - $CyNMos$), if $A \subseteq n$ - $CyNcl(n$ - $CyN\theta int(A)) \cup n$ - $CyNint(n$ - $CyN\delta cl(A))$.

The complement of a n - $CyNMos$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta os$, n - $CyN\delta Pos$, n - $CyN\delta Sos$, n - $CyN\theta os$, n - $CyN\theta Sos$ & n - $CyNeos$) is called a n - $CyNM$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta$, n - $CyN\delta P$, n - $CyN\delta S$, n - $CyN\theta$, n - $CyN\theta S$ & n - $CyNe$) closed set (briefly, n - $CyNMcs$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cs$, n - $CyN\delta Pcs$, n - $CyN\delta Scs$, n - $CyN\theta cs$, n - $CyN\theta Scs$ & n - $CyNecs$)) in X .

The family of all n - $CyNMos$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta os$, n - $CyN\delta Pos$, n - $CyN\delta Sos$, n - $CyN\theta os$, n - $CyN\theta Sos$ & n - $CyNeos$) of X is denoted by n - $CyNMOs(X)$, (resp. n - $CyNMCS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta OS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta CS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta POS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta PCS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta SOS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta SCS(X)$, n - $CyN\theta OS(X)$, n - $CyN\theta CS(X)$, n - $CyN\theta SOS(X)$, n - $CyN\theta SCS(X)$, n - $CyNeOS(X)$ & n - $CyNeCS(X)$).

Definition 2.30. [1] Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n - $CyNts$ and $A = \{ \langle x, \alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be an n - $CyNS$ in X . Then, the n - CyN

- (i) M -interior (resp. n - $CyN\delta$ -interior, n - $CyN\delta P$ -interior, n - $CyN\delta S$ -interior, n - $CyN\theta$ -interior, n - $CyN\theta S$ -interior & n - $CyNe$ -interior) of A (briefly, n - $CyNMint(A)$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta int(A)$, n - $CyN\delta Pint(A)$, n - $CyN\delta Sint(A)$, n - $CyN\theta int(A)$, n - $CyN\theta Sint(A)$ & n - $CyNeint(A)$) is defined by n - $CyNMint(A)$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta int(A)$, n - $CyN\delta Pint(A)$, n - $CyN\delta Sint(A)$, n - $CyN\theta int(A)$, n - $CyN\theta Sint(A)$ & n - $CyNeint(A)$) = $\bigcup \{ G : G \subseteq A$ and G is a n - $CyNMos$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta os$, n - $CyN\delta Pos$, n - $CyN\delta Sos$, n - $CyN\theta os$, n - $CyN\theta Sos$ & n - $CyNeos$) in X }.
- (ii) M -closure (resp. n - $CyN\delta$ -closure, n - $CyN\delta PP$ -closure, n - $CyN\delta S$ -closure, n - $CyN\theta$ -closure, n - $CyN\theta S$ -closure & n - $CyNe$ -closure) of A (briefly, n - $CyNMcl(A)$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cl(A)$, n - $CyN\delta Pcl(A)$, n - $CyN\delta Scl(A)$, n - $CyN\theta cl(A)$, n - $CyN\theta Scl(A)$ & n - $CyNecl(A)$) is defined by n - $CyNMcl(A)$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cl(A)$, n - $CyN\delta Pcl(A)$, n - $CyN\delta Scl(A)$, n - $CyN\theta cl(A)$, n - $CyN\theta Scl(A)$ & n - $CyNecl(A)$) = $\bigcap \{ K : K \subseteq A$ and K is a n - $CyNMcs$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cs$, n - $CyN\delta Pcs$, n - $CyN\delta Sn$ - $CyN\theta cs$, n - $CyN\theta Scs$ & n - $CyNecs$) in X }.

Definition 2.31. [2] Let (X, τ_1) and (Y, τ_2) be any two n - $CyNts$'s. A map $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ is said to be a n - CyN

- (i) δ -continuous map (briefly, n - $CyN\delta Cts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyN\delta os$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (ii) δ -pre continuous map (briefly, n - $CyN\delta P Cts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyN\delta Pos$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (iii) δ -semi continuous map (briefly, n - $CyN\delta S Cts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyN\delta Sos$ in (X, τ_1) ,

- (iv) θ -continuous map (briefly, n - $CyN\theta Cts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyN\theta os$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (v) θ -semi continuous map (briefly, n - $CyN\theta SCts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyN\theta S os$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (vi) e -continuous map (briefly, n - $CyNeCts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyNe os$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (vii) M -continuous map (briefly, n - $CyNM Cts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyNM os$ in (X, τ_1) .

Definition 2.32. [2] A map $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ is called a n -cylindrical neutrosophic M -irresolute (briefly, n - $CyNM Irr$) map if $f^{-1}(B)$ is a n - $CyNM os$ in (X, τ_1) for every n - $CyNM os(B)$ of (Y, τ_2) .

3. Contra M -Continuous Maps in n - $CyNts$

We will introduce n -cylindrical neutrosophic contra M -continuous maps and look at some of its feature in this section.

Definition 3.1. Let (X, τ_1) and (Y, τ_2) be any two n - $CyNts$'s. A map $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ is said to be a n - CyN contra

- (i) δ -continuous map (briefly, n - $CyN\delta Cts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyN\delta cs$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (ii) δ -pre continuous map (briefly, n - $CyN\delta PCts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyN\delta P cs$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (iii) δ -semi continuous map (briefly, n - $CyN\delta SCts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyN\delta S cs$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (iv) θ -continuous map (briefly, n - $CyN\theta Cts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyN\theta cs$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (v) θ -semi continuous map (briefly, n - $CyN\theta SCts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyN\theta S cs$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (vi) e -continuous map (briefly, n - $CyNeCts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyNecs$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (vii) M -continuous map (briefly, n - $CyNM Cts$ map), if the inverse image of every n - $CyNos$ in (Y, τ_2) is a n - $CyNM cs$ in (X, τ_1) .

Example 3.2. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4 in (X, τ_1) and B in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$A_1 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}$$

$$A_2 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}$$

$$A_3 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}$$

$$A_4 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}$$

$$B = \{\langle y_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle\}$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}MCts$ map.

Proposition 3.3. The statements are true, but the converse need not be true.

- (i) Every n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\theta Cts$ map is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}Cts$ map,
- (ii) Every n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\theta Cts$ map is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\theta SCts$ map,
- (iii) Every n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\theta SCts$ map is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}MCts$ map,
- (iv) Every n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta Cts$ map is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}Cts$ map,
- (v) Every n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta Cts$ map is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta PCts$ map,
- (vi) Every n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta Cts$ map is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta SCts$ map,
- (vii) Every n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta SCts$ map is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}eCts$ map,
- (viii) Every n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta PCts$ map is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}MCts$ map,
- (ix) Every n -CyN $\mathcal{C}MCts$ map is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}eCts$ map.

Proof.

- (i) Let B be a n -CyNos in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\theta Cts$ map, $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN θcs (X, τ_1) . Since every n -CyN θcs are n -CyN cs . $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN cs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}Cts$ map.
- (ii) Let B be a n -CyNos in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\theta SCts$ map, $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN θcs (X, τ_1) . Since every n -CyN θcs are n -CyN θSCs . $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN θSCs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\theta SCts$ map.
- (iii) Let B be a n -CyNos in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\theta SCts$ map, $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN θSCs (X, τ_1) . Since every n -CyN θSCs are n -CyN MCs . $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN MCs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}MCts$ map.
- (iv) Let B be a n -CyNos in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta Cts$ map, $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN δcs (X, τ_1) . Since every n -CyN δcs are n -CyN cs . $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN cs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}Cts$ map.

- (v) Let B be a n -CyNos in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta$ Cts map, $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN δ cs (X, τ_1) . Since every n -CyN δ cs are n -CyN δ Pcs. $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN δ Pcs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta$ P Cts map.
- (vi) Let B be a n -CyNos in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta$ Cts map, $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN δ cs (X, τ_1) . Since every n -CyN δ cs are n -CyN δ Scs. $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN δ Scs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta$ S Cts map.
- (vii) Let B be a n -CyNos in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta$ S Cts map, $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN δ Scs (X, τ_1) . Since every n -CyN δ Scs are n -CyNecs. $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyNecs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}e$ Cts map.
- (viii) Let B be a n -CyNos in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta$ P Cts map, $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyN δ Pcs (X, τ_1) . Since every n -CyN δ Pcs are n -CyNMcs. $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyNMcs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}M$ Cts map.
- (ix) Let B be a n -CyNos in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}M$ Cts map, $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyNMcs (X, τ_1) . Since every n -CyNMcs are n -CyNecs. $f^{-1}(B)$ is n -CyNecs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}e$ Cts map.

Remark 3.4. From the above mentioned results. We get the diagram below.

Note: $A \rightarrow B$ denotes A implies B , but not conversely.

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4 in (X, τ_1) and B in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ A_2 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_3 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}, \\ A_4 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ B &= \{\langle y_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is n - $CyN\mathcal{C}Cts$ map but not n - $CyN\mathcal{C}\theta Cts$ map, because the set $f^{-1}(B) = A_1$ is a n - $CyNcs$ but not n - $CyN\theta cs$.

Example 3.6. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, A_5 in (X, τ_1) and B in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ A_2 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_3 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}, \\ A_4 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_5 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle\}, \\ B &= \{\langle y_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is n - $CyN\mathcal{C}\theta Scts$ map but not n - $CyN\mathcal{C}Cts$ map, because the set $f^{-1}(B) = A_5$ is a n - $CyN\theta Scs$ but not n - $CyN\theta cs$.

Example 3.7. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4 in (X, τ_1) and B in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ A_2 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_3 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}, \\ A_4 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ B &= \{\langle y_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is n - $CyN\mathcal{C}MCts$ map but not n - $CyN\mathcal{C}\theta Scts$ map, because the set $f^{-1}(B) = A_1$ is a n - $CyNMcs$ but not n - $CyN\theta Scs$.

Example 3.8. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4 in (X, τ_1) and B in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ A_2 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_3 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}, \\ A_4 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ B &= \{\langle y_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}Cs$ map but not n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta Cs$ map, because the set $f^{-1}(B) = A_4$ is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}cs$ but not n -CyN δcs .

Example 3.9. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets A_1, A_2, A_3 in (X, τ_1) and B in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ A_2 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}, \\ A_3 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ B &= \{\langle y_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta P Cs$ map but not n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta Cs$ map, because the set $f^{-1}(B) = A_3$ is a n -CyN $\delta P cs$ but not n -CyN δcs .

Example 3.10. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, A_5 in (X, τ_1) and B in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ A_2 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_3 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}, \\ A_4 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_5 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ B &= \{\langle y_1, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta S Cs$ map but not n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta Cs$ map, because the set $f^{-1}(B) = A_5$ is a n -CyN $\delta S cs$ but not n -CyN δcs .

Example 3.11. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, A_5 in (X, τ_1) and B in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ A_2 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_3 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}, \\ A_4 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_5 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ B &= \{\langle y_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}eCts$ map but not n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta SCts$ map, because the set $f^{-1}(B) = A_5$ is a n -CyN eCs but not n -CyN δSCS .

Example 3.12. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, A_5 in (X, τ_1) and B in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ A_2 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_3 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}, \\ A_4 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_5 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle\}, \\ B &= \{\langle y_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}MCts$ map but not n -CyN $\mathcal{C}\delta PCts$ map, because the set $f^{-1}(B) = A_5$ is a n -CyN MCs but not n -CyN δPcs .

Example 3.13. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets $A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, A_5, A_6$ in (X, τ_1) and B in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ A_2 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_3 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}, \\ A_4 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_5 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}, \\ A_6 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}, \\ B &= \{\langle y_1, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{C}eCts$ map but not n -CyN $\mathcal{M}Cts$ map, because the set $f^{-1}(B) = A_6$ is a n -CyN eCs but not n -CyN Mcs .

Theorem 3.14. A map $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ is n -CyN $\mathcal{M}Cts$ map iff the inverse image of each n -CyN eCs in (Y, τ_2) is n -CyN Mos in (X, τ_1) .

Proof. Let B be a n -CyN eCs in (Y, τ_2) . This implies B^c is a n -CyN os in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is n -CyN $\mathcal{M}Cts$. $f^{-1}(B^c)$ is n -CyN Mcs in (X, τ_1) . Since, $f^{-1}(B^c), f^{-1}(B)$ is a n -CyN Mos in (X, τ_1) .

Conversely, let B be a n -CyN eCs in (Y, τ_2) . Then, B^c is a n -CyN os in (Y, τ_2) . By hypothesis $f^{-1}(B^c)$ is n -CyN eCs in (X, τ_1) . Since, $f^{-1}(B^c) = (f^{-1}(B))^c$. $(f^{-1}(B))^c$ is a n -CyN Mcs in (X, τ_1) . Therefore, $f^{-1}(B)$ is a n -CyN Mos in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{M}Cts$.

Definition 3.15. A n -CyN t (X, τ_1) is said to be n -cylindrical neutrosophic $MU_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (briefly, n -CyN $MU_{\frac{1}{2}}$)-space, if every n -CyN Mos in (X, τ_1) is a n -CyN os in (X, τ_1) .

Theorem 3.16. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be a n -CyN $\mathcal{M}Cts$ map, then f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}eCts$ map if (X, τ_1) is a n -CyN $M_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space.

Proof. Let B be a n -CyN os in (Y, τ_2) . Then, $f^{-1}(B)$ is a n -CyN Mcs in (X, τ_1) , by hypothesis. Since, (X, τ_1) is a n -CyN $MU_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space, $f^{-1}(B)$ is a n -CyN eCs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{M}Cts$ map.

Theorem 3.17. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be a n -CyN $\mathcal{M}Cts$ map and $g : (Y, \tau_2) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_3)$ be a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}eCts$ map, then $g \circ f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_3)$ is a n -CyN $\mathcal{M}Cts$ map.

Proof. Let A be a n -CyN os in (Z, τ_3) . Then, $g^{-1}(A)$ is a n -CyN os in (Y, τ_2) , by hypothesis. Since, f is a n -CyN $\mathcal{M}Cts$ map, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(A))$ is a n -CyN Mcs in (X, τ_1) . Hence, $g \circ f$ is a n -CyN $\mathcal{M}Cts$ map.

Theorem 3.18. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be a n -CyN $\mathcal{C}MCts$ map. The following conditions are then satisfied

- (i) $f(n\text{-Cy}NMcl(A)) \supseteq n\text{-Cy}Nint(f(A))$, for all $n\text{-Cy}Ncs(A)$ in (X, τ_1) ,
- (ii) $n\text{-Cy}NMcl(f^{-1}(B)) \supseteq f^{-1}(n\text{-Cy}Nint(B))$, for all $n\text{-Cy}Ncs(B)$ in (Y, τ_2) .

Proof.

- (i) Since, $n\text{-Cy}NMcl(f(A))$ is a $n\text{-Cy}NMcs$ in (Y, τ_2) and f is $n\text{-Cy}N\mathcal{C}MCts$ map, then $f^{-1}(n\text{-Cy}NMcl(f(A)))$ is $n\text{-Cy}NMos$ in (X, τ_1) . Now, since $A \supseteq f^{-1}(n\text{-Cy}Nint(f(A)))$, $n\text{-Cy}NMcl(A) \supseteq f^{-1}(n\text{-Cy}NMint(f(A)))$. Therefore, $f(n\text{-Cy}NMcl(A)) \supseteq n\text{-Cy}Nint(f(A))$.
- (ii) By replacing A with B in (i). We obtain $f(n\text{-Cy}NMcl(f^{-1}(B))) \supseteq n\text{-Cy}Nint(f(f^{-1}(B))) \supseteq n\text{-Cy}Nint(B)$. Hence, $n\text{-Cy}NMcl(f^{-1}(B)) \supseteq f^{-1}(n\text{-Cy}Nint(B))$.

4. Contra M -irresolute Maps in $n\text{-Cy}Nts$

We will introduce n -cylindrical neutrosophic contra M -irresolute maps and look at some of its feature in this section.

Definition 4.1. A map $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ is called a n -cylindrical neutrosophic contra M -irresolute (briefly, $n\text{-Cy}N\mathcal{C}MIrr$) map if $f^{-1}(B)$ is a $n\text{-Cy}NMcs$ in (X, τ_1) for every $n\text{-Cy}NMos(B)$ of (Y, τ_2) .

Theorem 4.2. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be a $n\text{-Cy}N\mathcal{C}MIrr$ map, then f is a $n\text{-Cy}N\mathcal{C}MCts$ map. But not conversely.

Proof. Let f be a $n\text{-Cy}N\mathcal{C}MIrr$ map. Let B be any $n\text{-Cy}Nos$ in (Y, τ_2) . Since, every $n\text{-Cy}Nos$ is a $n\text{-Cy}NMos(B)$ is a $n\text{-Cy}NMos$ in (Y, τ_2) . $\implies f^{-1}(B)$ is a $n\text{-Cy}NMcs$ in (X, τ_1) . Hence, f is a $n\text{-Cy}N\mathcal{C}MCts$ map.

Example 4.3. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets $A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, A_5, A_6$ in (X, τ_1) and B_1, B_2 in (Y, τ_2) are defined as

$$A_1 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\},$$

$$A_2 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\},$$

$$A_3 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\},$$

$$A_4 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\},$$

$$A_5 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\},$$

$$B_1 = \{\langle y_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\},$$

$$B_2 = \{\langle y_1, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle y_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}.$$

Then, we have $\tau_1 = \{0_X, 1_X, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_Y, 1_Y, B_1\}$. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then, f is $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}M\mathcal{C}ts$ map but not $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$ map, because the set B_2 is a $n\text{-CyN}M\mathcal{O}s$ in (Y, τ_2) $f^{-1}(B_2)$ is not $n\text{-CyN}M\mathcal{C}s$ in (X, τ_1) .

Theorem 4.4. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$ map, then f is a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}Cts$ map if (X, τ_1) is a $n\text{-CyN}MU_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space.

Proof. Let B be a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{O}s$ in (Y, τ_2) . Then, B is a $n\text{-CyN}M\mathcal{O}s$ in (Y, τ_2) . Therefore, $f^{-1}(B)$ is a $n\text{-CyN}M\mathcal{C}s$ in (X, τ_1) , by hypothesis. Since, (X, τ_1) is a $n\text{-CyN}MU_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space. $f^{-1}(B)$ is a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}s$ in (X, τ_1) . Hence f is a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}Cts$.

Theorem 4.5. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ and $g : (Y, \tau_2) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_3)$ be a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$ map, then $g \circ f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_3)$ is a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$ map.

Theorem 4.6. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$ map and $g : (Y, \tau_2) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_3)$ be $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}M\mathcal{C}ts$ map, then $g \circ f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_3)$ is a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}M\mathcal{C}ts$ map.

Proof. Let A be a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{O}s$ in (Z, τ_3) . Then, $g^{-1}(A)$ is a $n\text{-CyN}M\mathcal{O}s$ in (Y, τ_2) . Since, f is a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(A))$ is a $n\text{-CyN}M\mathcal{C}s$ in (X, τ_1) . Hence, $g \circ f$ is a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}M\mathcal{C}ts$.

Theorem 4.7. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ and $g : (Y, \tau_2) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_3)$ be a mappings. Then, $g \circ f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_3)$ is

- (i) $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}M\mathcal{C}ts$ if f is $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}Irr$ and g is $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}M\mathcal{C}ts$,
- (ii) $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$ if f is $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$ (resp. $n\text{-CyN}MIrr$) and g is $n\text{-CyN}MIrr$ (resp. $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$).

Theorem 4.8. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ and $g : (Y, \tau_2) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_3)$ are $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}M\mathcal{C}ts$ mappings and (Y, τ_2) be a $n\text{-CyN}MU_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space. Then, $g \circ f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_3)$ is $n\text{-CyN}M\mathcal{C}ts$.

Theorem 4.9. Let $f : (X, \tau_1) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_2)$ be a map. Then the following conditions are equivalent if (X, τ_1) and (Y, τ_2) are $n\text{-CyN}MU_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space.

- (i) f is a $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$ map,
- (ii) $f^{-1}(B)$ is a $n\text{-CyN}M\mathcal{O}s$ in (X, τ_1) for each $n\text{-CyN}M\mathcal{C}s(B)$ in (Y, τ_2) ,
- (iii) $n\text{-CyN}cl(f^{-1}(B)) \supseteq f^{-1}(n\text{-CyN}int(B))$ for each $n\text{-CyN}S(B)$ of (Y, τ_2) .

5. Conclusions

In this paper, by using $n\text{-CyN}M\mathcal{O}s$ we introduced $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}M\mathcal{C}ts$ and $n\text{-CyN}\mathcal{C}MIrr$ maps are analyzed and studied its properties.

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